

Soil Image Classification Using 1D Convolutional Neural Network with Flatten-Dropout Layer

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ABSTRACT

Soil classification plays a pivotal role in applications such as agriculture, construction, and environmental management. This paper aims to classify soil into three distinct categories: sandy, stony, and sticky using a custom 1D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with Flatten-Dropout Layer trained from scratch. Unlike traditional image classification methods that rely on pre-trained models, this work focuses on developing a custom CNN architecture that learns the key features specific to soil images directly from the raw data. The model is trained using a dataset of soil images, and the proposed custom CNN automatically learns from scratch allows it to extract relevant patterns and learn characteristics of different soil types, providing a tailored solution for soil classification tasks. The proposed method leverages the power of deep learning to perform soil classification with high accuracy. The custom CNN is trained using early stopping criteria. Performance metrics and classification accuracy is used to evaluate the model's effectiveness. The proposed custom CNN model has achieved training accuracy of 91.21%, validation accuracy of 87.18% and test accuracy of 89.74% which is quite satisfactory.

KEYWORDS: *Soil Classification, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Flatten-Dropout Layer*

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil classification is a fundamental aspect of agriculture, civil engineering, and environmental studies. Understanding the types of soil and their properties is crucial for planning these aspects. Examining soil as a material can be the start of soil classification [1]. Soil structure is directly related to the sharpness, shape, spatial arrangement of key particles. Soil can be broadly categorized into different types based on its physical and chemical properties. Among the most common types of soils are Sandy (Figure 1), Sticky (Figure 2) and Stony (Figure 3). Different combinations of these three soils images are taken into consideration in this paper.

Figure 1. Sandy soil

Figure 2. Sticky soil

Figure 3. Stony soil

Traditionally, many methods were used in the laboratory and in the field such as pipette method, the elutriation method etc. to determine soil texture and color. The disadvantage of these methods is the laborious and time consuming. Therefore, soil classification has attracted the attention of researchers on the use of automated methods based on Machine Learning, Deep Learning [9], [10] especially CNNs [2] in soil classification.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The initial step in soil classification involves gathering diverse soil test images, as emphasized by Riese and Keller [1] who highlighted the importance of selecting appropriate sensor data. In their study, An et al. [2] proposed that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are highly effective for soil classification tasks due to their ability to learn complex feature relationships directly from raw image data. The architecture of CNNs was further elaborated by Velichko [3], who explained that these models utilize multiple layers, such as convolutional and pooling layers, to extract and integrate data at varying levels of abstraction. Dubey et al. [4] highlighted the adaptability of CNNs, noting that during inference, these networks leverage learned representations to analyze previously unseen images and predict their respective classes. To enhance the precision and effectiveness of CNNs, Keerthi et al. [5] recommended the use of techniques such as data augmentation and batch normalization. A hybrid approach combining CNNs with Genetic Algorithm (GA) was proposed by Byerly et al. [6]. Inspired by natural evolutionary processes, GA explores complex solution spaces to identify near-optimal configurations. However, as noted by Basri et al. [7], the performance of CNNs heavily relies on the fine-tuning of hyperparameters, such as learning rates, network topologies, and regularization strategies. Finally, the potential of using readily available tools, such as smartphone cameras for soil analysis was demonstrated by Aitkenhead et al. [8]. In conclusion, the literature survey reveals that many authors have utilized pretrained models for soil classification tasks, leveraging their ability to generalize across datasets. However, in this paper, we focus on building a custom model tailored specifically to the unique characteristics of our dataset.

3. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology employs CNNs to classify soil images into three categories: sandy, sticky, and stony. The methodology involves:

3.1 Data Collection and Pre-processing

Data collection is a very crucial part of this research. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of our soil classification model, we collected high-resolution soil images under controlled conditions using a Moto G54 5G smartphone camera. The images were captured with the following technical and environmental specifications:

- Average Dimensions: 8192x6144 pixels
- Average File Size: 6.9 MB per image
- Aperture: f/1.8, allowing optimal light capture for fine texture and detail visibility.
- ISO: 100, ensuring minimal noise and high clarity.
- Flash: No flash was used to preserve the natural texture and color of the soil samples
- White Balance: Set to Auto for consistent color representation
- Exposure Time: 1/769 s, preventing motion blur and overexposure
- Environment_Temperature: Approx 25°C
- Location: 26.5497255°N, 88.6948730°

The collected images were later processed for resizing, augmentation and converted to another color spaces to prepare them for training the proposed CNN model.

3.2 Proposed Custom CNN Model Design

The proposed method involves designing and implementing a custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to classify soil types (sandy, stony, sticky) using a preprocessing pipeline that ensures effective feature extraction and robust classification performance. Hyperparameters are responsible for increasing the efficiency of our proposed model. The architecture of the custom CNN model is shown in Figure 4. Detailed description of proposed CNN Architecture is given below in Table-1. Moreover, Table-2 shows used hyperparameters in our proposed CNN model.

Figure 4. Proposed CNN Architecture

Table 1: Description of Proposed CNN Architecture

Type (Symbol)	Kernel Size	Filters	Activation Function	Drop rate
INPUT(IN)	—	—	—	—
Convolutional layer 1(CL-1)	3x3	32	Swish	—
Max Pooling 1(PL-1)	2x2	—	—	—
Convolutional layer 2(CL-2)	3x3	64	Swish	—
Max Pooling 2(PL-2)	2x2	—	—	—
Convolutional layer 3(CL-3)	3x3	128	Swish	—
Max Pooling 3(PL-3)	2x2	—	—	—
Convolutional layer 4(CL-4)	3x3	512	Swish	—
Max Pooling 4(PL-4)	2x2	—	—	—
Flatten (FLAT)	—	—	—	—
Fully Connected Layer 1(FL-1)	—	128	Relu	—
Dropout(DROP)	—	—	—	0.5
Fully Connected Layer 2(FL-2)	—	128	Relu	—
Output Layer(OUT)	—	3	Softmax	—

Table 2: Hyper-parameter of Proposed CNN Architecture

Hyperparameters	Value
Learning rate	0.001
No. of Epoch	50
Batch Size	32
Optimizer	Adam
Loss Function	Categorical_cross-entropy

3.3 Training, Validation and Testing Data

The entire dataset (i.e. soil images) is divided into training, validation and testing dataset. The training dataset is used to train the proposed CNN model and monitor the proposed model's classification ability on seen images in each epoch. The validation dataset is used to predict by our trained model to compare the training accuracy with validation accuracy so that proposed model can avoid overfitting or underfitting issues. The Test dataset, kept entirely separate from training and validation, was used for the final evaluation of the model after the entire training process.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we have discussed the platform-tools, results and other conditions that have been used for training and testing of proposed model.

4.1 Platform and Tools

The development environment was Google Colab and sample images were stored in Google drive for training. The custom CNN model is implemented using Python as the primary programming language, leveraging popular libraries such as TensorFlow, Keras, OpenCV, NumPy, and Matplotlib libraries for building and training the CNN. Following configuration has been used: Processor: Google Colab GPU (Tesla T4), Operating System: Linux-based environment provided by Google Colab.

4.2 Early Stopping Criteria

To prevent overfitting-underfitting and optimize training time, an early stopping mechanism was implemented using a custom callback function at the end of every epoch. Training was halted if both the training and validation accuracy reached 85% or higher at a particular epoch. If somehow during training early stop criteria aren't triggered, then we can use stored weight values in which we got the best training and validation accuracy at a specific epoch.

4.3 Results

The entire dataset about 390 sample images are divided into training and validation and testing dataset as 70:20:10 ratios. In training, validation dataset, test dataset there are 273 (91 images each for 3 types of soil), 78 (26 images each for 3 types of soil) and 39 (13 images each for 3 types of soil) data respectively.

Figure 5. Training accuracy vs epoch

Figure 6. Validation accuracy vs epoch

In the above Figure 5 and 6, graphs depict the training and validation accuracy trends across 42 epochs. As we can see, the early stop criterion is triggered at epoch no. 42 out of 50.

4.3.1. Training Accuracy

Figure 5 shows a steady improvement in training accuracy and reaching approximately 0.92 by the 42th epoch. We got 249 (83 sandy images + 91 sticky images + 75 stony images) out of 273 is correct and 24 (8 sandy images + 16 stony images) are incorrectly predicted. Moreover, a confusion matrix based on

above predictions is given below in Figure 7. It is able to achieve a good training accuracy of 91.21% with training loss of 8.79%.

4.3.2. Validation Accuracy

Figure 6 illustrates the validation accuracy occasionally peaks at values close to 0.9. We got 68 (24 sandy images + 26 sticky images + 18 stony images) out of 78 is correct and 10 (2 sandy images + 8 stony images) are incorrectly predicted. Also we got a confusion matrix based on predictions shown in Figure 8 and achieved a good validation accuracy of 87.18% with validation loss of 12.82%.

4.3.3. Testing Accuracy

We have used a testing image dataset which gave results 35 (11 sandy images + 13 sticky images + 11 stony images) out of 39 is correct and 4 (2 sandy images + 2 stony images) are incorrectly predicted. Moreover, we have got a confusion matrix based on predictions shown in Figure 9 and achieved a good testing accuracy of 89.74% with testing loss of 10.26%.

Figure 7. Confusion matrix for Training Figure 8. Confusion matrix for Validation Figure 9. Confusion matrix for Testing

4.4 Comparative Study:

The results of the proposed model are compared with the existing model based on testing as shown below in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparing result based on testing Dataset

Methods	Accuracy (%)
Proposed CNN	89.74
[1]	73
[2]	99.70
[3]	80
[4]	94.24
[6]	99.81

From above Table 3, the result shows that the proposed model performs better than the existing model [1], [3] for testing dataset. It reflects our proposed CNN model’s efficiency. However testing accuracy is

inferior compared to the existing work [2], [4], [6]. In future we shall try to improve the classification accuracy further.

5. CONCLUSION

This work successfully demonstrates that by designing and training a custom CNN model from scratch, we were able to extract and utilize soil-specific features, achieving accurate and efficient soil images classification with approx 90% classification accuracy. The results illustrate the effectiveness of deep learning in handling complex visual patterns that are difficult to discern manually, thereby surpassing traditional soil classification methods in both accuracy and scalability. The implications of this work extend to critical areas such as agriculture, construction, and environmental management, where rapid and precise soil analysis is essential. The developed model's ability to adapt to new datasets and its scalability make it a robust tool for real-world applications. Future enhancements could focus on expanding the dataset for greater generalization, integrating additional soil properties like textures, and deploying the model in field-ready systems to facilitate on-site soil analysis. multi-dimensional CNNs can also be used to enhance the proposed model performances.

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